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Thermo-physiology and thermal protection of clothed human body with continuous sweating under radiant heat: a sweating manikin study

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Introduction

Heat stress under radiant heat has been an important topic for occupational exposure and general public health, especially in the context of global warming [1]. This study builds on the idea of combined analyses of thermo-physiological effect and thermal protective performance of clothing, which greatly influences the heat and moisture transfer of human body. Previous studies usually investigated the two clothing thermal characteristics separately, and thus, only provide one-sided information on heat transfer. Besides, sweat vapour transfer was considered in most of these studies neglecting liquid sweat transfer. Such approach may lead to an inadequate evaluation of thermal risks for human body. Thus, we performed a series of studies to understand the heat transfer (evaporative cooling and radiant heat gain) and moisture transfer (sweat evaporation, accumulation and dripping) of clothed human body during continuous liquid sweating under radiant heat.

Methods

Experiments were performed in a climatic chamber (20.0 ± 0.5 °C, 50 ± 2 %) with a sweating torso manikin [2] at sweat rates of 100, 175 and 250 g/h. Twelve protective clothing systems (7 single layer material: SU, R_{ct} : 10.8 - $16.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{W}$, R_{et} : 2.0 - $4.4 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{Pa}/\text{W}$; 5 multilayer material: TG, R_{ct} : 46.6 - $95.4 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{W}$, R_{et} : 9.4 - $23.9 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{Pa}/\text{W}$) were selected and wrapped around the cylindrical torso without inclusion of air gap. Each experiment included three consecutive phases, with a constant torso surface temperature of 35 °C for each phase. In phase 1 (P1), the torso was in dry state for one hour. In phase 2 (P2), a pre-set sweat rate was applied for two hours duration. In phase 3 (P3), torso was irradiated unilaterally (front side) by a radiant heat panel with an intensity of $1 \text{ kW}/\text{m}^2$ for another two hours while the sweat rate was kept at its previous level. The amount of total sweating, sweat accumulation and dripping sweat were recorded continuously through balances. The total heat loss (THL) in P2 and P3, apparent evaporative heat loss and radiant heat gain were obtained as heat transfer indicators. The sweat evaporation rate (\dot{m}_{evap}), absorption rate and dripping rate were calculated as moisture transfer indicators. Effects of radiant heat, sweat rate and material properties on these heat and moisture transfer indicators were analyzed. In addition, by combining the heat and moisture transfer data in P2, apparent evaporative cooling efficiency (η) and heat transfer components caused by sweating were discussed.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 (a) presents THL of clothed torso manikin in environment without radiant heat (P2) and with radiant heat (P3) at three sweat rates. It shows how the effect of radiant heat on heat dissipation interacts with amount of perspired moisture and material properties. A dual effect of perspired moisture was quantified. That is, for hydrophilic materials, sweating induced evaporative cooling but also increased radiant heat gain probably due to wet conduction but for hydrophobic materials, perspired moisture slightly increased evaporative cooling and decreased the radiant heat gain. These results provide experimental evidence that thermal and evaporative resistances, the general indicators of the clothing thermo-physiological impact, have limitations in characterizing heat stress during active liquid sweating in radiant heat. Material hydrophilicity, emissivity and thickness are also necessary to consider, e.g., Fig.1 (a) shows effects of

material hydrophilicity and emissivity at similar thermal and evaporative resistances of single and multi-layer samples, respectively [3].

Furthermore, \dot{m}_{evap} increases with sweat rate and the increase is affected by material properties.

Evaporative resistance of materials alone is limited to characterize the evaporation process from clothed human body with continuous sweating under radiant heat. Material hydrophilicity, water accumulation capacity and emissivity are also crucial factors to determine \dot{m}_{evap} as shown example in Fig.1 (b). In addition, radiant heat can increase or decrease \dot{m}_{evap} depending on material structures, revealing possible steam burn mechanism [4].

Figure 1. Total heat loss (a), evaporation rate (b), and apparent evaporative cooling efficiency (c) of clothed torso manikin in environment without radiant heat (P2) and with radiant heat (P3) at three sweat rates, where phi: hydrophilic materials, pho: hydrophobic materials, ϵ : material emissivity.

We also quantified the sweating cooling power components and environmental evaporative heat during continuous sweating. It shows that the effect of perspired moisture on η is different between SU and TG and also influenced by material hydrophobicity as shown example in Fig.1 (c). The increase of perspired moisture played an opposite role in η for hydrophilic Sus (Fig.1 (c)), which may be due to the balance between evaporative area and evaporative locus. For hydrophilic TGs, η is negatively correlated with fabric evaporative resistance. For hydrophilic Sus and TGs, $\Delta\eta$ from sweat rate 100 to 175g/h linearly decreased with increasing fabric thickness. [5]. Besides, based on combined analyses of moisture transfer rate and η , we provided hypotheses of dynamic steady moisture transfer for different material systems [4].

Conclusions

This series of studies contributes to the understanding of heat and moisture transfer in clothed human body with continuous sweating under radiant heat. It draws attention to the previously unconsidered critical role of liquid sweating in the two-way heat transfer and key material thermal and moisture management properties rather than traditional resistance indicators. It updates the knowledge of clothing thermal characteristics and thermal behaviors of clothed human body and will benefit development of protective material and improve thermal comfort and safety in occupational and general exposures.

References

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